

Charting the impact of circular economy projects: the DEFINITE-CCRI approach

Eleni Kanellou^{1*}, Evi Makri¹, Mathijs Nelemans², Marijana Novak²,

¹*School of Electrical & Computer Engineering, National Technical University of Athens, Athens, Greece*

²*Circle Economy, Amsterdam, The Netherlands*

*Corresponding author: ekanelou@epu.ntua.gr

The EU strives to transition to a circular economy model to reduce the pressure on natural resources, to create sustainable growth and jobs, and to achieve its 2050 climate neutrality target to stop the loss of biodiversity (1). The 2015 Circular Economy Action Plan (CEAP) outlines the measures to support the transition of the EU in ways that safeguard healthy competition conditions, sustainable economic growth, the opening of new jobs or career opportunities across the EU (2). Circular economy, which is directly connected with the Sustainable Development Goal of responsible consumption and production (3), lies at the heart of the European approach, that has defined the concept as “an economy where the value of products, materials and resources is maintained in the economy for as long as possible, and the generation of waste is minimised” (4).

Despite the importance of such a transition and of the existing policies aiming at enabling it, investments in circular economy projects are not yet mainstreamed. In fact, there is a gap between project owners that develop circular economy solutions and investors. The DEFINITE-CCRI approach comes to bridge this gap and to support circular economy projects to become more attractive to potential investors and help them to secure the required funds. The DEFINITE-CCRI approach provides a holistic methodology in order to support the circular economy projects that includes a financial, technical and innovation, and impact potential assessments. Initially interested projects are assessed on their financial viability, on the technical and innovation potential as well as on the impact they have on an environmental, social, and macro-economic level. Then the projects are given recommendations and a set of services to advance their maturity and make them more attractive to investors. Finally, the projects are brought in touch with investors to pitch their circular economy projects and secure funding.

Assessing the impact of circular economy projects can be a complex process, due to the interrelations of a broad variety of factors. The scope of the DEFINITE-CCRI methodology is to assess the impact of circular economy projects with regards to their circularity potential, and the environmental, social, and macro-economic impact they have on a local level. The approach to assess the impact is based on the 9R strategies and is in line with the EU Circular Economy Action Plan, the EU bioeconomy strategy, and the EU taxonomy.

More specifically, within the DEFINITE-CCRI approach a framework has been developed to assess the impact and innovation potential of circular economy projects (5). The projects that are being assessed are examined regarding factors such as their technological readiness and innovation potential, as well as their circularity performance and their impact potential on environmental, social, and macro-economic domains. To effectively do the assessment a formalized form has been created (part of it can be seen in the following table), that is easy to customise per project regarding the required data input needed for assessing their impact or/and potential impact on the aforementioned domains.

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The required information includes the material groups that are used, e.g., biomass, metals, non-metallic minerals, fossil fuels. It also includes information on solid waste and the waste generation types, e.g., chemical, and medical wastes, recyclable wastes etc. Then information on water consumption is needed, followed by information on energy composition. Finally details on the operations and the technology employed are also required. After the data have been gathered, indicators are calculated to assess the impact of projects.

This holistic approach enables projects to showcase in an easy way the impact they have or aim to have on a local level, bringing them one step closer to acquiring the investments needed to proceed with the solution by showcasing the actual impact potential on a circularity, environmental, social and macro-economic levels.

Table 1. Total Material Inputs

Table M.1: Material inputs in tonnes							
Material groups	M1.1	M1.2	M1.3	M1.4	M1.5	M1.6	M1.7
	Volume of Inputs	Share of inputs that are virgin materials (volume)	Share of inputs that are secondary materials (volume)	Total volume (materials/waste) collected for processing (that would have otherwise gone for landfill)	Share of materials that are imported (volume)	Share of materials sourced nationally (volume)	Share of materials sourced on site (volume)
	Tonnes	%	%	%	%	%	%
Biomass							
Metals							
Non-metallic minerals							
Fossil fuels							
Total							

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Key words: circular economy; 9R strategies; impact assessment; circularity; investment.